

PP 112: Achieving a triple benefit – A Monthly Health Initiative at Regional Directorate of Health Services(RDHS) Colombo for Wellness Promotion

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Background:

Recognizing the importance of orienting on preventive healthcare services and employee well-being, Regional Directorate of Health Services Colombo initiated a monthly health promotion programme for its employees

Description of the initiative:

Discussions were made with all units regarding the new initiative and allocated a monthly 40- minute time slot on the last Friday of the month, during lunch hour for the health promotion programme. A technical committee was appointed to select the timely topics for each month and to decide modes of presentations

Lessons Learnt:

Lessons Learnt: Regular workplace health promotion at RDHS offices serves a triple benefit-enhancing well-being, staff members being healthcare messengers and they getting to know the services offered by the healthcare institutions.

Keywords: Workplace health screening; Preventive healthcare; Employee wellness; Health promotion; Public health awareness.

Methods used for Evaluation:

Number of monthly sessions conducted and number of staff members participated were used for evaluation.

Results:

The first health promotion programme, held on April 11, 2025, covered key health topics such as metabolic syndrome, Health Lifestyle clinic services, Well Woman Clinic services; PAP smears tests, self-breast examination, and vector-borne diseases. Following this session, a Non-Communicable Disease (NCD) screening programme including blood pressure, height, weight, BMI, Vision, blood sugar measurements and calculation of 10-year cardiovascular risk was conducted for 55 employees. Session was completed after giving personalized health advice to the non-medical employees by medical officers. The feedback from the employees highlighted the fact that important health messages were passed to the general public through family members of the employees. Furthermore, they appreciated the services offered by the health staff of healthcare institutions and suggested topics to be discussed in future sessions.